

THE ROLE OF CUSTOMS VALUE IN COLLECTING CUSTOMS DUTIES (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE CUSTOMS DEPARTMENT OF THE TASHKENT CITY)

Z.O. Kuvatova

Customs Institute of the State Customs Committee Tashkent, Uzbekistan

zahrokuvatova@gmail.com

Abstract: the area of customs and tariff regulation of foreign economic activity, namely, the influence of customs value on the calculation and collection of customs payments, is considered from a scientific point of view to be a poorly studied area of economic science. In the context of current trends in the development of the world economy, the study of this issue is particularly relevant. Based on the conducted analysis, the importance of exercising control over the correct determination of the customs value and its role for calculating and collecting customs payments is revealed. In the course of the investigation, the causes and consequences of problematic issues that hinder the perfect functioning of customs value control were studied.

Keywords: customs value, fiscal function, customs tariff regulation, methods of determining customs value, customs payments, import duty, export duty, special customs duties, seasonal duties, customs duty rates.

In the context of the globalization of the market economy and the sustainable development of trade relations, the role of the state occupies a special places an active regulator, which is a key component of improving the world economy. The customs authorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan, represented by the state, implementing a free customs policy, in order to achieve customs goals and perform functional duties, assume the role of the main tool in the intensive development of world trade turnover and increase financial transactions, thereby maintaining the balance chain between the interests of states, business and final consumption.

Based on the fact that the fiscal function of customs authorities, aimed at ensuring financial stability and replenishing the state budget by calculating and collecting customs payments, the role of customs value in improving the potential of the international economic environment is a requirement today. Therefore, the main purpose of this article is to determine the customs value and its role in the mechanism of collecting customs payments.

In the context of the country's transition to a market economy, it became necessary to create a stable customs and tariff regulation of foreign economic activity as an integral part of the state administration system. Customs and tariff regulation of foreign economic activity (FEA) is understood as a set of organizational, economic, and legal measures carried out in accordance with the procedure established by law by state bodies and aimed at regulating foreign economic activity.[1]

Customs tariff regulation is an important and time-consuming process that involves several interrelated operations: determining the country of origin of goods; determining the customs value of goods; and paying customs duties.

The purposes of applying customs and tariff regulation measures may be:

The protectionist function - is the protection of national producers from foreign competition.

Fiscal function - is ensuring the receipt of funds to the state budget.

Regulatory - has a certain influence on the formation of the structure of production, on the pricing mechanism, encourages the development of some industries and hinders the development of others.

Trade and political (which can also be considered as an element of the regulatory function) - is an instrument of indirect influence on the economic policy of other states, plays a certain role in achieving a balance of economic interests between countries. [2]

Based on the above, it is assumed that the main basic element for performing one of the main tasks of customs authorities, which is carried out through tariff regulation to ensure the formation of the revenue part of the republican budget through the accrual and collection of customs payments, is the control of customs value. The procedure for determining the customs value is generally accepted, based on the principles common to all countries, prescribed in the International Agreement on Tariffs and Trade of 1994 (GATT). Article 7 of the GAAT deals with the evaluation of goods for the purpose of collecting Customs duties. It establishes the principles common to all participating countries for determining the customs value of goods and states that the customs value of goods should be based on its actual value and cannot be determined on the basis of arbitrary fictitious estimates or the value of goods of domestic origin. The concept of customs value is defined as the transaction value, i.e. the price actually paid or payable for goods sold for export to the country of import, adjusted for the possibility of adding.

The determination of the customs value of goods applied in the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on general principles applied in international practice. According

to the Customs Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the customs value of goods imported into the customs territory is the value of goods determined by one of the methods of determining the customs value of goods and used for calculating customs payments.

The customs value of goods is determined for the purpose of taxing goods with customs payments, maintaining foreign trade statistics and special customs statistics, and applying other measures of state regulation of foreign economic activity, including currency control.

The customs value of imported goods is determined by applying the following methods:

- by the value of the transaction with the imported goods;
- based on the transaction value of an identical product.
- based on the transaction value of a similar product.
- based on subtraction of costs.
- based on adding up the costs.
- reserve.

The main method for determining the customs value of imported goods is the method for the transaction value of imported goods. If the main method of determining the customs value of imported goods cannot be applied, the above methods are consistently applied. In this case, each subsequent method is applied if the customs value cannot be determined by using the previous one. The methods of subtraction and addition of values can be applied in reverse order. [22]

Figure 1. Application of methods for determining customs value according to the Department of the State Customs Committee of Tashkent city for the years of 2020-2021. (% of the amount of a gas turbine engine).

Based on the table, we can observe that the main share of CCD falls on 1, 6.1, 6.3 methods (for 2020 92.47% and for 2021 93.42%), where method 1 confidently takes the leading place (for 2020 38.61% and for 2021 42.79%). 3 method of determining the customs value in contrast to 2, 4, 5, 6.2, 6.4, 6.5 Russia ranks at the average level (7.14% for 2020 and 6.29% for 2021), while the latter have low indicators. The number of GTDs for 2021 increased in methods 1 and 6.1 методах in relation to 2020 (by 4.18 % and 2.12 % , respectively), while for the period of 2020, the indicators of methods 3 and 6.3 were higher than for 2021. It follows from this that the main share of the method of determining the customs value of processed goods is determined by applying 1, 3, 6.1, 6.3 OTC methods.

Thus, when calculating and collecting customs payments, the basis is the customs value of goods, which is determined by the methods of determining the customs value.

According to the Customs Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, while goods moving across the customs border and in other cases provided for by this Code, the following customs duties are paid:

- customs duty;
- value added tax;
- excise tax;
- customs fees.

Figure 2. Structure of customs payments of Department of the State Customs Committee of Tashkent city for the year 2021. (%).

The analysis of the table consists of the fact that for the period 2021 department of the state customs committee in the city of Tashkent, customs payments exceeded 48% of the amount of payments made by customs authorities throughout the republic. A large share of these respectively, is occupied by customs duties and value added tax (19.97% and 76.86%), low indicators are found in excise tax, customs duties, recycling fees and others (0.89%, 0.92%, 1.14 % and 0.22% respectively).

Based on the above, it is worth mentioning the importance of customs value control for calculating and collecting customs payments. Thus, customs value is used as the basis for the taxation of goods with customs duties and taxes calculated at the ad valorem rate, or at the ad valorem component of the combined rate of customs duties and taxes.²³

Customs costs indirectly affect the competitiveness of goods. Underestimation of the customs value leads to underestimation of customs payments and, as a result, underestimation of the value of goods on the domestic market of the Republic of Uzbekistan in comparison with the value of goods for which payments were paid in full. This leads to increasing in the competitiveness of goods imported by an unscrupulous foreign economic activity participant compared to other goods. [²⁴]

T. Pardaev, A. Shadmankulov, Z. Makkamov. Customs payments. Textbook (in Uzbek). T.: Customs Institute - 2021..

Article from the customs broker website "Customs value control"

A. Shadmankulov. Fundamentals of regulation of foreign economic activity (part I).

In the course of monitoring the correctness of determining the customs value, customs authorities are forced to resort to using the average market price for the relevant product. In conditions when a fairly limited number of foreign trade participants are involved in the import of specific goods, collusion between suppliers may occur, which leads to the appearance of unreliable information from customs authorities regarding the average customs value.

The importance of correctly stating the customs value of goods imported into the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan lies in the fact that when moving consignments of goods, albeit small ones, across the customs border, it is possible that the declarants' unfair attitude to determining the customs value of the goods being moved is not excluded. As a result, the state suffers significant losses in the form of non-replenishment of the state budget. After all, it should be remembered that a significant share of funds in the state budget comes as a result of the activities of customs authorities. As a result, the state does not receive enough money and cannot fully develop in the future.²⁵

In the figure below, we can observe the amount of additional customs payments for certain areas of activity of customs authorities. It is worth noting that the customs value, although it occupies a low indicator in comparison with other areas, but this indicator ultimately leads to large shortfalls in customs payments, underestimation of the customs value of goods in the database of customs authorities, which leads to violations of customs legislation.

Figure-3. The structure of additionally accrued customs duties at the Department of the State Customs Committee of Tashkent city. (% , 2021 year).

The value of the customs value is directly affected by: global and state trends in the socio-economic situation, customs duty rates, risk behavior of foreign trade participants and customs officials, the content and quality of the procedure for determining and controlling the customs value. It should be concluded that the control of the correctness of determining the customs value when calculating and collecting customs duties it has a special place.

Nowadays, in practice, there is a whole range of problems associated with incorrect determination of the customs value, for example, manipulation of the customs value, as well as many issues in the application of the methods of calculating it established in the legislation. Participants in foreign economic activity began to apply various schemes of false declaration, when unscrupulous declarants provide information that does not reflect the actual value of the transaction, and declare false information about the customs value of goods, the purpose of which is to evade customs payments. In modern terminology, the concept of "gray import" has appeared, meaning the import of goods with undervalued customs payments due to their unreliable declaration or the import of goods in addition to customs control. The consequences of which led to the practice of underestimating the customs value of goods. Such as, falsification of foreign economic contracts, invoices and other shipping documents submitted in support of the customs value, or declaration of goods under a different name is used. The solution to this issue may be to maintain a register of unfair customs brokers, in addition, to automatically record the facts of providing false information in the unified register of unfair declarants.

However, currently, based on the indicators for 2020-2021, almost only two of them are used: the first and sixth. This case reduces the possibility of determining the actual customs value of goods more accurately, which, accordingly, reduces the efficiency of customs authorities. The problem of exchange rate differences that arises when the currency of the price and the currency of payment do not match.

In the practice of customs clearance, we can observe how due to changes in the exchange rate of the contract currency reflected in commercial documents, in relation to the currency of payment (amounts), the risk management system issues a risk in fact beyond the lower customs value of goods, in most cases methods for determining the customs value, where reference is made to an earlier issued import declaration. Such circumstances are not a violation of customs legislation, but lead to a decrease in the efficiency of time allocation by a customs officer to the customs clearance process, and will also affect the non-application of simplification of customs

procedures when registering a cargo customs declaration. The solution to this problem will be the improvement of risk management system of automated information system for determining the customs value, by implementing format-logical control when the exchange rate changes. On the basis of a mechanism that will operate in the principle of linking and comparing the invoice values, the country of departure, vehicles at departure, the value per unit of goods of the submitted customs declaration with the declaration referred to or with the goods referred to by the presented goods when determining the index of customs value per unit of goods.

In addition, one of the main problems in determining and controlling the customs value is that in the era of digitalization, the interstate partnership for the exchange of information and information on shipping and transport documents has not reached the necessary level, which leads to a lack of verification of the correctness of the information provided, as well as the lack of practice of providing documents in electronic form, this prevents the possibility of implementing format-logical control over them, thereby leaving this task to the human factor. The solution to this issue is the introduction of unified communication systems between the customs authorities of foreign countries, primarily with countries with which Uzbekistan has close interstate trade and economic relations, fixed by bilateral and multilateral agreements, the results of which are accompanied by a large flow of goods exchange, exchange and informatization of documents and information provided. These countries include China, Turkey, Europe and the CIS.

The results of the study revealed a qualitative and quantitative analysis of the relevance of the topic of the impact of the customs value of goods on the correct calculation and collection of customs duties. During the study, ideas on digitalization of customs operations, as well as integration of customs authorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan with other foreign institutions of control of foreign trade relations are proposed, which will serve as the results of the directions and tasks of the strategy for the development of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026.

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